

Synthesis and Characterization of Enhanced Luminescent Properties of CdTe Quantum Dots

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Abstract

Quantum Dots (QDs) are semiconductor nanoparticles which have unique optical and photo physical properties. These properties make them widely to be used for fabrication of photovoltaics, optoelectronic devices such as solar cells, electrodes in Liquid Crystal Display (LCD's), Light Emitting Diodes (LED's) and Laser Diodes. Synthesis of quantum dots with increased quantum yield has proved helpful for optoelectronic applications. In this present work, the CdTe quantum dots are synthesized by aqueous phase medium with the Mercaptosuccinic acid (MSA) used as a capping agent. The reaction parameters were optimized to produce highly luminescent MSA-CdTe quantum dots. The size dependent optical properties of MSA-CdTe quantum dots were revealed by UV-Vis absorption analysis. The result shows that the calculated band gap value of the CdTe quantum dots are decreasing with the increase in refluxing time. Emission properties of MSA-CdTe quantum dots were revealed by photoluminescence analysis. Optical band gap values of MSA-CdTe quantum dots for different refluxing time was calculated from the emission spectra obtained. The FTIR analysis confirms the capping of MSA on to the surface of CdTe quantum dots and peaks obtained stands well in agreement with bonding of MSA to CdTe. The crystalline structure of the prepared MSA-CdTe quantum dots were studied by X-Ray diffraction analysis which confirms the cubic zinc blende structure. Thermal stability of MSA-CdTe QDs was analyzed by TGA. Hydrodynamic diameter of MSA capped CdTe QDs was found in the range of 3-10 nm by using DLS. HRTEM results shows the CdTe QDs are having the range of 2-5 nm. The result will be discussed in detail.

Keywords: Quantum Dots, Mercapto succinic acid, Optical Properties, Photoluminescence.

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